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Questionnaire

Gender equality in the governing boards of national sports federations of Europe

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This questionnaire is addressed to all members of sport governing boards and can be completed by both men and women. The research is funded by the European Union Erasmus+ Sport Project programme. The project is entitled “Corporate Governance in Sports Organizations: A Gendered Approach”. This questionnaire is also being carried out simultaneously in Italy, Portugal, Turkey, the United Kingdom and Spain. It aims to understand gendered experiences in national sport governing bodies’ boards. It should take no more than around 10 minutes to complete.

All responses will be kept confidential and your anonymity protected. If you have any questions please contact to the email address: gesport@unizar.es

If you do not know the answer to any question, please leave it blank and continue to the next one. Thank you for sharing your thoughts and taking the time to help us with our project. If you give consent to take part in this questionnaire then please click “Next” to begin.

Please visit: <http://gesport.unizar.es/> for more information on the project.

Below is the link to the questionnaire translated into each of the five languages of the project using Google.

[ENGLISH](#) - [ITALIAN](#) - [PORTUGUESE](#) - [SPANISH](#) - [TURKISH](#)

